

DESIGN, FABRICATION AND TESTING OF THE HELICOPTER TAIL ROTOR BLADE FROM COMPOSITE LAMINATED MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: In this paper the design, fabrication and analysis of behavior by full-scale verification testing for the tail rotor blade of composite laminated materials for a heavy transport helicopter is given.

The verification test program for the tail rotor blade encompassed static and dynamic testing. The static tests of the blade involved experimental evaluation of torsional and flexional blade stiffness and its elastic axis position. Dynamic tests involved testing of vibratory characteristics and testing of blade fatigue characteristic. In structural vibration tests natural frequency, vibration modes and damping ratio for the structure were measured. The fatigue analysis of the structure of blade root section was performed after fatigue test cycles for detection of laminate separation, tolerance and distortion of crosssections of structure.

KEYWORDS: Design, Fabrication, Verification Full-Scale Testing, Helicopter Tail Rotor Blade, Composite Laminated Materials.

INTRODUCTION

In general, high-performance composites exhibit high strength and stiffness, low density, and good resistance to fatigue and corrosion, properties that make them very well suited to many aircraft and aerospace applications. The use of fiber-reinforced composites in flight critical structures in helicopters is growing rapidly. But, the introduction of composites has not been without problems. These include development of entirely new design, fabrication, and qualification discipline, difficulty in analyzing internal stresses, demonstrating this technology to certifying agencies, determination of adequate test criteria, and quantifying environmental degradation [1,2].

The development and qualification of the helicopter components and system includes a heavy emphasis on a full-scale test approach independent from the design process. In the case of fatigue-loaded flight-critical components, a laboratory fatigue program is conducted, supported by static

DESIGN AND FABRICATION

A development of a tail rotor blade was performed in four phases: (1) the blades design on the working station using designing system Howard-Hughes and automated Gerber-marker making system (see Figure 3), (2) preparation and cutting of blade components on the Gerber-Garment cutting system (Figures 4-6), (3) blade manufacturing in a two-section metal die (Figure 7), and (4) final verification testing.

In the blade manufacturing procedure the conventional composite materials with epoxy resin matrix, a fiberglass filament spar, an eighteen-section skin of laminated fabrics (Figure 4), some carbon filament embedded along the trailing edge, a core, leading edge protection strips of polyurethane and stainless steel etc. were used. All the used materials are standard products

fabricated at Ciba-Geigy, Interglas GmbH, Torayca and others [6].

Fig. 2: The heavy transport helicopter tail rotor.

Each blade paddle consists of a fiberglass-epoxy spar and a fiberglass blade section which is fastened to the outboard end of the spar. Unidirectional fiberglass-epoxy is used to provide a high modulus in the axial direction and adequate torsional stiffness for full pitch change motion of the blade. Similarly, flapping (out-of-plane) motions are accommodated through elastic bending of the spar.

The spar cross section provides the high edgewise (in-plane) stiffness required for an aeroelastically stable rotor.

Fig.3: Automated Gerber-marker making system.

The inboard or torque tube portion of the blade is not supported by core and is designed to provide high torsional rigidity. The trailing edge contour of the airfoil is formed by a continuous structural pocket which has a Rohacell polyurethane foam core and a fiberglass skin. The upper and lower skins are fabricated from woven fiberglass that is laid up with the fibers oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ and $0^\circ/90^\circ$ to the blade longitudinal axis. On the blades, the inplane blade natural frequency is tuned by stiffening the trailing edge of lower skin with some carbon filaments.

Fig.4: The sections of a skin woven.

The leading edge contour is formed by a fiberglass leading edge piece which is protected from erosion by a combination of "C" shaped stainless steel and polyurethane erosion strips which are bonded to the blade leading edge. A series of counterweights are bonded to the leading edge of the spar to provide the required chordwise blade balance. The counterweights are moulded of elastomer with lead shot embedded in the matrix of fiberglass with lead rod in the laminate. The counterweights fill the area between the leading edge piece and spar [6].

In assembly, the first process is to cut the fiberglass fabrics to the require shape and stacking it to build up the required shapes (see Figures 4-6).

Next stage, is wovenwrap and placed it in a matched metal tool, together with the fiberglass filament spar, uncured trailing edge skins, the Rohacell polyurethane foam core and tool transferred to heated platten press (see Figure 7).

Fig.5: By computer prepared the woven sections for cutting.

The resin (Ciba-Geigy Type) used in blade manufacture is cured in two stages. In the first the component is warmed (70°C to 90°C , the duration of 2 hrs) until the resin becomes fluid. The matrix is then consolidated and shaped by pressure. This reduces the bulk of the material drives out included air. The component may then be fully cured by raising the temperature to 120°C (1 hr).

Fig.6: Automated Gerber-Garment cutting facility.

TESTING AND RESULTS

The verification test program for the helicopter blade encompassed static and dynamic testing [3]. The static tests of the tail blade involved experimental evaluation of torsional and flexional blade stiffness and its elastic axis position. Dynamic tests involved testing of vibratory characteristics and

verification testing of blade fatigue properties.

Fig. 7: Matched aluminium die

The purpose of the static tests was to evaluate experimentally torsional and flexional stiffness and elastic axis position of the blades. The employed techniques and methods at the testing are the usual practice at all aerospace research centers.

To fit the blade model, a robust facility frame made of steel *L* and *U*-profiles was employed. For load application, i.e. for force and torque, an airfoil clamp and system of wheels and cables mounted on a special frame made of steel profiles were used (Figure 8). For displacement measurement, comparators with an accuracy of 0.01 *mm* were used.

Fig. 8: Load-introduction airfoil clamp in static testing.

To determine the blade torsional stiffness one needs to define the required torsional moment in the ruling cross-section that would cause torsion of one radian relative to the blade root cross-section.

At torsional testing a low-intensity torque M was applied to the blade by means of the airfoil clam in order to preserve linearity. Blade leading/trailing edge measuring displacements were measured with comparators. Based on the measurements, torsional angles Θ at selected blade cross-sections along its span were calculated. The results for the investigated blade are presented in Table 1 for the marked cross-section (Figures 8 and 9) and the torsional stiffness were calculated as:

$$m_{\Theta} = \frac{dM}{d\Theta} \text{ [daNm / rad]}$$

The average values of the torsional stiffness obtained from the measurements with the following applied torque: $M=1.96; 3.92; 5.89; 7.85$ and 9.81 [daNm], are presented in Table 1.

Fig. 9: Measurement points in static and vibratory testing.

Flexional tail rotor blade stiffness can be determined from the expression:

$$m_d = \frac{F l^2}{f} \text{ [daNm/rad]}$$

where F is applied force, $l=1.6 \text{ m}$ - distance between the applied force and blade fitting point, f - deflection of the elastic axis. The measuring point locations along the blade span were the same as those for the case of torsional testing. Based on these measurements, position and deflection of the blade elastic axis were determined. The elastic axis position for the blade is presented in Table 1. Practically, for all cross-sections of the blade, elastic axis position was located 33.6 percent of blade cross-section's airfoil cord.

Table 1: Tested results for the tail rotor blade

Type of the blade	Tail rotor
Type of core	polyurethane foam
Elastic axis position, x/c	0.336
Average values of torsional stiffness m_{θ_m} [daN m/rad]	541.62
Average values of flexional stiffness m_{d_m} [daN m/rad]	2640.17
first mode f_1 [Hz]	8.2
second mode f_2 [Hz]	40.2
third mode f_3 [Hz]	98.2
fourth mode f_4 [Hz]	162.7
d ($x_m=65 \text{ cm}$)	0.0117
Q -factor ($x_m=65 \text{ cm}$)	40

Based on the deflection measurement at the leading/trailing blade edge's selected cross-sections, the elastic axis deflection was calculated. Consequently, the calculated values of the elastic axis deflections were utilized for calculation of the flexional stiffness for the blade. The results with averages of the flexional stiffness for the selected, marked cross-section for the blade is presented in Table 1 (Figure 9).

The aim of the tail rotor blade vibratory testing program was to determine the blade main aeroelastic properties. The program included determination of the natural oscillation modes and the

structure's natural frequency and also valuation of blade structural damping for the foam (Rohacell) core.

The main components of the test facility and testing equipment used during the investigations are consisted of two functionally connected sections: excitation apparatus and response-detection equipment.

The excitation apparatus consisted of a pulse generator, a signal amplifier, a digital timer/frequency counter, a vibration exciter (shaker) and an airfoil clamp for force introduction. The response-detection equipment included: piezoelectric accelerometers, an oscilloscope, a waveform analyzing system, and a multichannel $X-t$ recorder.

The same blade as those for the static testing were used. The measuring points were located along the blade elastic axis as shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 10: Natural modes of oscillation for the tail rotor blade.

In the experiment a pulse generator, with a sinusoidal excitation function and with a precise adjusting of frequency set-point value in a range from 0.01-10000 Hz, was used. A digital frequency counter was used for precise read-out of excitation frequency. The exciter was electrodynamic one that is considered to be the most suitable for conducting a harmonic analysis and this type of experiment. The link between the exciter and the rotor blade was formed of an aluminium alloy pipe with an adjustable length and by use of a panel airfoil clamp that was shaped so as to fit the blade local cross-section at the location of application of excitation. For displacement measurements at the blade selected points (Figure 9), the piezoelectric sensors were used. The special cement was used to intimately stick the pick-up to the surface of blade.

In these investigations, as a first step, a harmonic analysis for the blade was performed. Having determined the frequencies for the first-four harmonic's natural (resonant) modes of oscillations, displacement vectors for the first-four oscillation modes were measured. Figure 10 shows the results of the harmonic analysis of the first-four harmonics for the blade with foam Rohacell core.

Rotor blade structural damping was determined from amplitude reduction of free vibration. The blades were excited to vibrate with the first (resonant) oscillation mode with continuously decreasing amplitude due to damping effects.

The logarithmic decrement of the free vibrations was utilized to characterize the structural damping diagram (Figure 11). Its value was determined as:

$$d = \frac{1}{n} \ln \frac{x_k}{x_{k+n}}$$

where $n=10$ is the number of observed oscillations, x_k is observed initial amplitude in the time interval, whereas the correspondent average value of amplitude is:

$$x_m = \frac{1}{2} (x_k + x_{k+n})$$

Q -factor is also usually used to define the structural damping and gives relative energy (E) reduce in successive oscillations. Q -factor is defined as:

$$Q = \frac{E_1}{E_1 - E_2} \approx \frac{1}{2d}$$

The comparative presentation of the results of the structural damping for the blade, expressed by the logarithmic decrement and the Q -factor are given in Figure 11.

Fig. 11: Logarithmic decrement and Q -factor of the tail rotor blade.

The fatigue test program of the helicopter blades included: interlaminar separation (delamination) testing and geometric deformation of the blade cross-sections following the fatigue tests program during which real rotor blade loads were simulated - the same loads to which blade is exposed under extreme flight conditions [1-3].

The inboard and root section of the rotor blades is usually tested as a simple cantilever beams. Simulated centrifugal load is applied and an eccentric and crank arm is used to apply bending loads. The blades are oriented at an angle to the plane of motion of the eccentric arm so that combined flatwise and chordwise bending loads are simultaneously applied. The program and the way in which these investigations were carried out on the rotor blades represents a standard practice followed by majority of scientific and research aeronautical institutions [2-7].

In the course of the rotor blades attachment fatigue testing program, a very robust facility frame made of steel U and L -profiles tied together with screws was used (Figure 12).

The applied test loads include simulated steady centrifugal, vibratory chordwise bending, vibratory flapwise bending, and vibratory torsional pitch motion. The cyclic load consists of flapping and lagging loads with simultaneous application of centrifugal force.

The simulated forces' values were: the centrifugal force 11350 daN , while resulting excitation alternating variable load (flapp/lag-originated cyclic load) that was vertical to the rotation plane and originated from vibratory chordwise bending, vibratory flapwise bending and vibratory torsional pitch

motion, had the value of 500 daN at the 6.5 Hz (390 rpm) frequency and at the angle of excitation force of 18° .

Facility test frame used in the helicopter rotor blades fatigue testing was composed of several basic modules: facility to which helicopter rotor blade was attached and fixed, the excitation group and modules for centrifugal force simulations (Figure 12).

Fig. 12: The blade in fatigue testing.

The blade attachment module enabled the rotor blades to be fixed into the facility frame and provided an attachment link between the rotor blade and the facility frame thus enabling blade adjustments according to the angle of excitation force. The link was formed by two plates and a double tapered spindle. The front plate had the angle of excitation force graduation and the front nut enabled the blade to be securely fixed. The back plate and the nut completely secured the link from being unscrewed. Additional means used to prevent any eventual loosening was a slotted bar with the inverted slider-crank mechanism placed at the area of attachment.

The excitation group consisted of an electric motor with a rating of 2.2 kW and rotation speed of 1420 rpm , a belt drive with transmission ratio of 1:3, variable speed drive (variable reduction gear), with a transmission ratio 1-3.25, eccentric mechanism with an adjustable eccentricity of $0-25 \text{ mm}$ and an eccentric crank arm with bonded strain gages for excitation for selection. The excitation arm is strain gaged and generation of the static load i.e. the centrifugal force, the section that transmitted the force to the blade root section and the blade root attachment fitting at which at one end centrifugal force was applied and at the same time the excitation force at the other end. A hydraulic servo-controlled actuator composed of a hydraulic cylinder, distribution system with oil lines and a pump with a servomotor and control manometer was used as the centrifugal force generator. Its maximum force was 40000 daN . Thanks to this system the basic functioning of the facility frame became automatic.

The homological fatigue testing program for the blade root involved, conforming to the standards [1-3], fatigue testing of six identical blades. This testing includes a program with simulated centrifugal force-relaxing loading. The blade models were investigated for the time-fatigue by applying excitation force at the 6.5 Hz frequency with simultaneous application of full-magnitude centrifugal force in duration corresponding to 1.5×10^6 cycles. After every 3×10^5 cycles the blade root relaxation was performed by gradually increasing and decreasing the intensity of the centrifugal force in a $0-11350-0 \text{ daN}$.

In the course of those investigations the behavior of the blades, was permanently and closely followed. No any damages or delamination of the structures, i.e. no any changes were observed in the course of the testing itself. When the fatigue testing program was finished on the blades, further detailed check-ups and controls in respect to the deformation and degradation of geometrical shape of the blades and delamination were carried out. On that occasion no any changes were observed on the blades.

CONCLUSION

Verification testing of composite aircraft components designed for low-weight, flight-critical applications are required to verify structural adequacy and/or to provide data for redesign. The failure observed in verification testing were generally not predicted by design analysis and were related to design details such as ply endings, holes, curved sections, bonded joints, and bolted joints.

Well-designed composite laminated structures can provide a high degree of damage tolerance and in practice it is still very difficult to utilize the full fiber strength potential of composite structures. The composite laminated materials give constructions with except-ionally high level of the structural damping so important in aircraft application.

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